

Is Narragansett Bay an ideal laboratory to study tides?

Ashfaq Ahmed^{1*}

¹Center for Fluids and Thermal Science, Brown University, Rhode Island, USA

Key Points:

- Differences of the tidal characteristics within the Bay
- Salinity variation due to river run-off
- Inter-annual variation of the environmental proxies

*Brown University, Providence, Rhode Island, USA 02906

Corresponding author: Ashfaq Ahmed, ashfaq_ahmed@brown.edu

Abstract

This brief article introduces a basic comparative analysis of the inter-annual variation in tide in two locations in Narragansett Bay and how they affect environmental indicators (such as salinity, chlorophyll, temperature, and dissolved oxygen). The data was collected from two stations: Phillipsdale (station 1), which is situated in a shallow water region and exposed to greater levels of human activity, and Conimicut Lighthouse (station 2), which is farther away from the urban area and preserves more natural conditions. In this talk, we investigated the possible impact of the annual variations in tidal elevations on environmental indicators, primarily focusing on salinity. The findings reveal that the average monthly tide heights are notably higher during early fall (August to October) than early spring (February to April). This further leads to increased horizontal flow, vertical upwelling, and turbulent mixing and results in salinity increases and chlorophyll blooms in both stations. As we advance, similar analyses will allow us to characterize the tidal nature of other estuaries of a similar kind, such as the Chesapeake Bay in Virginia.

1 Introduction

An estuary is a semi-enclosed coastal body of water typically formed where freshwater from rivers and streams mixes with saltwater from the ocean (Pritchard, 1967). Estuaries are among the most productive environments on Earth that create more organic matter (Canuel & Hardison, 2016) than equivalent grassland, forest, or agricultural land yearly. Classified by their geology, there are mainly four kinds of estuaries, and according to Raposa (2009), Narragansett Bay is a drowned river valley estuary. It is the largest estuary in New England (Wallace et al., 2014), with approximately 146 square miles in size (Jeffries & Terceiro, 1985) and is fed by several rivers, including the Seekonk, Blackstone, and Providence Rivers. The Bay is home to many coastal communities and a significant economic and recreational resource for Rhode Island. Several factors influence the Bay's ecosystem, including freshwater inputs, tidal exchange, and pollutants. Despite these challenges, the Bay supports a diverse array of marine life, including numerous fish species, shellfish, and migratory birds (Humphries et al., 2022).

From an ecological and environmental perspective, tides can significantly impact the salinity levels of coastal waters (Guo & Valle-Levinson, 2007). The salinity of an estuary can be strongly affected by several tidal factors, including the amount of freshwater exchanging the system (Reid, 1930). When tides are high, saltwater can travel further into estuaries and rivers, increasing the salinity levels in those areas. Conversely, when tidal waves are low, fresh water from rivers and other sources can mix with saltwater, lowering the salinity levels. Tides can also influence the overall mixing in different scales (Lee et al., 2009) and the circulation of water in a coastal area. Chambers et al. (1998) showed when tides are strong, they can help to distribute salt and other dissolved substances evenly throughout the water column, helping to maintain a consistent salinity profile. However, when tides are weak, this mixing may not occur, allowing for the buildup of areas with high or low salinity. In addition, tides can also affect the exchange of water between the ocean and the atmosphere (Godfrey, 1996), which can further influence the salinity levels in coastal waters. For example, during periods of high tide, water can be trapped in lagoons or Bays, leading to changes in the evaporation and, therefore, salinity. That being said, tides play a crucial role in determining the salinity levels of coastal waters and are essential to consider when studying an estuary like Narragansett Bay and its dynamic processes.

Many studies have been done on the tides, and tidal currents of Narragansett Bay (Nixon, 1989; Bowers & Brubaker, 2021; Tomas & Smayda, 2008; Spaulding & Swanson, 1974). Generally, the relationship between tides and salinity in estuaries is complex (Poffenbarger et al., 2011). It can vary depending on several factors, including the size

Table 1. Units for the environmental proxy

Proxy	Unit
Salinity	ppt
Temperature	°C
Dissolved Oxygen	mg/L
Chlorophyll	ug/L

Figure 1. Snapshot taken from Google map (02/14/2023) over Narragansett Bay, including some of the Rhode Island Sound. The boxed area shows our stations.

and shape of the estuary, the intensity and timing of tides, and the freshwater inputs from rivers and other sources. Estuaries are generally characterized by their dynamic and changing salinity levels (Whitfield, 1992), primarily driven by the interplay between ocean tides and freshwater inputs.

In addition, other profound factors, such as the intensity and timing of freshwater inputs, the overall size and shape of the estuary, and the presence of physical barriers, can also impact the salinity levels in the estuary. For example, suppose an estuary is large and has limited physical barriers. In that case, tides may be less effective at maintaining consistent salinity levels, and the system may be more susceptible to changes in freshwater inputs. Thus, the relationship between tides and salinity in estuaries is complex and dynamic, and it is essential to consider each estuary's unique characteristics and conditions when studying its salinity patterns. Therefore, in this study, we evaluated two stations with distinct geological features to understand the minute dissimilarities in the inter-annual average tide heights and their possible impacts on the Bay.

Figure 2. Water level (m) for the year 2020 (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration tide gage at Newport, Rhode Island). Data sample resolution: 1 hour.

Table 2. Tidal elevation (m) consistency statistics

Station and time	Mean sea water level (m)	Standard deviation (m)	Skewness
Station 1 (12:00 pm/am)	0.1615	0.4755	0.2837
Station 2 (12:00 pm/am)	0.1488	0.4594	0.3042
Station 1 (06:00 pm/am)	-0.1129	0.4749	0.1647
Station 2 (06:00 pm/am)	-0.1108	0.4564	0.1692

2 Study Area and Data

The first station of our study area is located at 41.8422°N , -71.3719°W , close to the Seekonk river, and the second station is situated at 41.7430°N , -71.3514°W , in the Providence river (Fig. 1). The tide data are collected from National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Tides and Currents. As for the salinity and other environmental parameters (i.e., chlorophyll), we obtained the data from the Narragansett Bay Commission. The tides and the salinity data have a sampling frequency of 1 hour. While the tide data is available in both stations for the entire of 2020, we noticed that the environmental proxy data for station 2 is only available from May to November. So, we analyzed the inter-annual variation of the representatives within this time frame. The units are given in Table 1.

3 Tidal Characteristics

One of the key goals of this article is to explain the characteristics of the tidal elevation in our selected stations. As an approach, we plotted Fig. 2 which represents the entire history of the sea water level (m) for the year 2020. From this, we can observe a high/low pattern within the monthly variation of tide heights. It is also noticeable that in both stations, there is no significant difference within this high/low pattern throughout the year. To provide with a deeper understanding at the tidal characteristics, Fig. 3 comes with histograms that connects us with the statistics of the diurnal pattern of the tides in the Bay. In both stations, during the noon and mid-night the sea water level are tend to be consistently higher (panel a and c). The opposite scenario is observed during 6 am/pm (panel b and d) where the average water level goes below the reference level [0 m]. 2 lays out the details statistics on these histograms. It is to be noticed that the frequency of the high tide is more skewed during the noon and mid-night indicating that the occurrence is more spreaded out with a long tail. The data from 6 am/pm shows the tendency to stay towards the center (0 m). The standard deviation is nearly the same for all the cases.

To study the hourly variation, we averaged the tidal elevation data for individual hour and plotted Fig. 3. panel (e). This graph is similar to a typical climatology, which indicates the expected sea level at any given time of the day. The graph is also indicating the presence of semi-diurnal tides in the Bay. Semi-diurnal tides, primarily caused by the gravitational forces of the Moon and the Sun, are a tidal pattern characterized by two high tides and two low tides per day, with approximately equal intervals between each. The maximum average high tide is up-to 0.15 m of water level rise and during the low tide the water level go below 0.14 m of the reference sea level on average. In Narragansett Bay, regardless of low or high, the elevations are generally higher at 12 am/pm than at 6 am/pm. This is in contrast to other types of tides, such as diurnal tides, which have only one high tide and one low tide per day, and mixed tides, which have a varying number of high and low tides per day.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Tide and Salinity

The relationship between tides and salinity is an important area of study for understanding the dynamics of coastal environments and the factors that influence their ecological and economic value. The inter-annual variability in sea level water influences the salinity in Narragansett Bay. After averaging the monthly tide data, as described in Fig. 4 (panel a), we find the average tide height in early fall (August to October) is much higher than that of early spring (February to April). Although both stations' monthly average tide height shows a similar trend, station 1's average during the winter (January to March) is less than that of station 2. It is probably because station 1 is located in a shallow water region with minimum river run-off. Thus, during the winter, the shore's average water level depth goes much below the reference sea level.

Now, let our concentration be on the salinity of the Bay. As previously mentioned, there is missing data from station 2, so we will have to observe the general trend of the available data (May to November) to interpret what is happening there. We aim to look for any pattern that might be affected by the tides. For the salinity, we observe frequent fluctuation in station 1. Salinity seems to jump from 1 ppt to almost 30 ppt within a short time frame. On the other hand, the average salinity of station 2 is pretty consistent throughout the available time series, and it is within 25 to 35 ppt, except for a few anomalies (Fig. 5, panel a). At this point, there could be two questions in the reader's mind, 1) why are the two stations showing different salinity characteristics? and 2) what is the indication that there is a signature of tidal influence behind this salinity trend? We need to go back to their locations to answer the first question. Station 1 is located in shallow water, close to the locality, and exposed to a narrow-channel river run-off. Most importantly, seawater can hardly reach that point without tidal influence. Notwithstanding, station 2 is closer to the open ocean and wide open to more saltiness, so the average salinity shows a slight variation over time. This discussion makes it clear that the tides will strongly determine the salinity of an area far from the deep ocean. Which essentially answers our second question too. To add more reasoning to this claim, we can look at the lower panel of Fig. 4 and it is clear that more sea water brings more salt in the Bay. During August to November there is a similar increasing trend in both cases. Thus, in summary, we can say the tide has a marked hold on the average salinity of the Bay, and any anomalies within the tidal cycle will directly influence the local ecology and communal activities.

4.2 Other Environmental Proxies

Although the fundamental purpose of this paper is to highlight salinity changes due to tidal influences, we will take the privilege to report on the other environmental indicators. A number of previous studies concentrated on the temperature records and their

Figure 3. Histograms of the frequency of tide height in both stations (a-d). Data are collected in four different periods of a day: 12 am, 6 am, 12 pm, and 6 pm. Tidal elevation plots indicates the presence of semi-diurnal tides in the bay.

Figure 4. Monthly average of the sea water level in meter (Panel a) and the salinity (Panel b) indicating more sea water brings the saltiness in the estuary.

Figure 5. The annual variations of the environmental proxies, a) salinity, b) temperature, c) dissolved oxygen, and d) chlorophyll). Data are collected and compared from both stations.

environmental impacts on Narragansett Bay (Jones et al., 1989; Karentz & Smayda, 1984; Nowicki, 1994). Benoit and Fox-Kemper (2021) critically analyzed a four-decade temperature data of the Bay and described how it is experiencing climatic warming, seasonal changes in effluents impacts, and thermal pollution due to the Brayton Point Power Station. As Fig. 5, panel b describes a generic climatology to temperature; we can find that signals from the temperature anomalies are stronger in station 1. This can happen for several reasons. First, the station is exposed to thermal pollution as some industries (i.e., Vitae Industries, AmSpec Service LLC) are nearby. Station 1 is also sensitive to the overall heat/thermal capacity because the water here is not very deep.

In Narragansett Bay aquatic ecosystems, the relationship between chlorophyll and dissolved oxygen is complex (Byron et al., 2011) and depends on a variety of factors, including the amount of organic matter, nutrients present (Deacutis, 2008), and the presence of other organisms. Chlorophyll is a photosynthetic pigment found in algae and other plants (Humphrey, 1980), and is often used as an indicator of phytoplankton abundance in aquatic ecosystems. At the same time, phytoplankton and algal bloom play an important role in the production of dissolved oxygen through photosynthesis, which involves the uptake of carbon dioxide and release of oxygen. Dissolved oxygen is a critical component of aquatic ecosystems, as it is necessary for the survival of fish and other aquatic organisms. Oxygen is consumed by organisms during respiration, and is also used during the decomposition of organic matter. We can see a decline in dissolved oxygen from Fig. 5, panel c during the summer and fall seasons. This is understandable because, within this time frame, algal blooms occur in the Bay and they use more oxygen for photosynthesis. We can be particular about the algal blooms because chlorophyll is a direct proxy for phytoplankton. Fig. 5, panel d demonstrates the sudden rise of chlorophyll in the Bay during this season. The variations of the inter-annual tidal elevation don't play a dominating role in the overall characteristics of the temperature, and chlorophyll because without any interruption from the outside (i.e., anthropogenic disturbance), the ecosystem is balanced and self-sustainable. A future research question is what would happen

if we considered the similar analyses for an extended period (i.e., 20 years). Another exciting research question can be whether the results are identical to any estuary with similar geometry (i.e., Chesapeake Bay, Virginia). Much could be derived from available data sources, and we expect to complete them along with the budget calculation in the upcoming papers.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we put effort into understanding the tidal nature of the Narragansett Bay based on the available data from two stations. We found a coherent relationship between the tide height anomalies and their potential impact on the Bay's salinity. The findings indicate that tides have a direct impact on the salinity in areas near the coastline. However, the opposite is not true, which means that if a location is farther south from the capital, the salinity will remain relatively constant throughout the year due to the continuous mixing with the saltwater. This implies that the location's proximity to the sea plays an important role in determining the impact of tides on the salinity of the Bay.

6 Acknowledgement

Ashfaq Ahmed acknowledges Dr. Baylor Fox-Kemper for his previous feedback on the Narragansett Bay tidal analysis for a nearly similar project. This work would not have been possible without using in-situ buoy data from <https://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/> and <http://snapshot.narraBay.com/app/Buoys/Export>.

References

- Benoit, J., & Fox-Kemper, B. (2021). Contextualizing thermal effluent impacts in narragansett bay using landsat-derived surface temperature. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 705204.
- Bowers, D., & Brubaker, J. (2021). Providential tides: the double low water of narragansett bay. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 44(1), 44–53.
- Byron, C., Link, J., Costa-Pierce, B., & Bengtson, D. (2011). Calculating ecological carrying capacity of shellfish aquaculture using mass-balance modeling: Narragansett bay, rhode island. *Ecological Modelling*, 222(10), 1743–1755.
- Canuel, E. A., & Hardison, A. K. (2016). Sources, ages, and alteration of organic matter in estuaries. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 8, 409–434.
- Chambers, R. M., Mozdzer, T. J., & Ambrose, J. C. (1998). Effects of salinity and sulfide on the distribution of phragmites australis and spartina alterniflora in a tidal saltmarsh. *Aquatic Botany*, 62(3), 161–169.
- Deacutis, C. F. (2008). Evidence of ecological impacts from excess nutrients in upper narragansett bay. *Science for Ecosystem-based Management: Narragansett Bay in the 21 st Century*, 349–381.
- Godfrey, J. (1996). The effect of the indonesian throughflow on ocean circulation and heat exchange with the atmosphere: A review. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 101(C5), 12217–12237.
- Guo, X., & Valle-Levinson, A. (2007). Tidal effects on estuarine circulation and outflow plume in the chesapeake bay. *Continental Shelf Research*, 27(1), 20–42.
- Humphrey, A. (1980). Chlorophyll. *Food Chemistry*, 5(1), 57–67.
- Humphries, A., Gorospe, K., Innes-Gold, A., McNamee, J., McManus, C., Oviatt, C., & Collie, J. (2022). In pursuit of ecosystem-based management for narragansett bay: An overview of previous models and roadmap for future research. *Coastal Management*, 50(3), 262–283.
- Jeffries, H. P., & Terceiro, M. (1985). Cycle of changing abundances in the fishes of the narragansett bay area. *Marine ecology progress series. Oldendorf*, 25(3),

- 239–244.
- Jones, D. S., Arthur, M. A., & Allard, D. J. (1989). Sclerochronological records of temperature and growth from shells of *mercenaria mercenaria* from narragansett bay, rhode island. *Marine Biology*, 102, 225–234.
- Karentz, D., & Smayda, T. J. (1984). Temperature and seasonal occurrence patterns of 30 dominant phytoplankton species in narragansett bay over a 22-year period (1959–1980). *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*, 18, 277–293.
- Lee, I.-H., Lien, R.-C., Liu, J. T., & Chuang, W.-s. (2009). Turbulent mixing and internal tides in gaoping (kaoping) submarine canyon, taiwan. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 76(4), 383–396.
- Nixon, S. W. (1989). An extraordinary red tide and fish kill in narragansett bay. In *Novel phytoplankton blooms: causes and impacts of recurrent brown tides and other unusual blooms* (pp. 429–447).
- Nowicki, B. L. (1994). The effect of temperature, oxygen, salinity, and nutrient enrichment on estuarine denitrification rates measured with a modified nitrogen gas flux technique. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 38(2), 137–156.
- Poffenbarger, H. J., Needelman, B. A., & Megonigal, J. P. (2011). Salinity influence on methane emissions from tidal marshes. *Wetlands*, 31(5), 831–842.
- Pritchard, D. W. (1967). What is an estuary: physical viewpoint..
- Raposa, K. B. (2009). Ecological geography of narragansett bay. *An Ecological Profile of the Narragansett Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve*, 77–88.
- Reid, D. (1930). Salinity interchange between sea-water in sand and overflowing fresh-water at low tide. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 16(2), 609–614.
- Spaulding, M. L., & Swanson, C. (1974). Tides and tidal currents of narragansett bay.
- Tomas, C. R., & Smayda, T. J. (2008). Red tide blooms of *cochloclodium polykrikoides* in a coastal cove. *Harmful algae*, 7(3), 308–317.
- Wallace, R. B., Baumann, H., Grear, J. S., Aller, R. C., & Gobler, C. J. (2014). Coastal ocean acidification: The other eutrophication problem. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 148, 1–13.
- Whitfield, A. (1992). A characterization of southern african estuarine systems. *Southern African Journal of Aquatic Science*, 18(1-2), 89–103.